

ISic1458

I.Sicily inscription 1458

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

tuff

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance

Necropolis of Manicalunga

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8747

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Οἶμοι

2. ὃ Λυκίω

3. κε

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284895

EDR 112423

EDCS 41300062

EDCS 64800248

PHI 175674

Bibliography

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